

The Influence of Product Quality, Price and Promotion to Increase Customer Satisfaction at Queen Cempaka Hills Housing

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 20 August 2024</p> <p>Corresponding Author: Nurul Qomariah</p>	<p>Customer satisfaction is an important thing that must receive attention for service provider organizations. If customers are satisfied then there will be good recommendations. This research aims to determine the impact of product quality, price and promotion on customer satisfaction at Queen Cempaka Hills Jember Housing. The research population is all consumers who bought a house at Queen Cempaka Hills Jember Housing. The sample plan was determined to be 30 respondents. Description analysis, validity and reliability tests and hypothesis testing were carried out for this research. The research results are expected to show that product quality, price and promotion have a positive effect on customer satisfaction at Queen Cempaka Hills Jember Housing.</p>
<p>KEYWORDS: product quality; price; promotion; housing area.</p>	

INTRODUCTION

The housing industry is one sector that continues to experience growth and is increasingly developing in Indonesia. The housing industry referred to is the industry related to the development, construction, sales and management of residential properties. The housing industry itself is very important and has an influence on the economy because it has a significant impact on other sectors, such as the financial, banking, construction and trade sectors. The growing development of the housing industry also goes hand in hand with the challenges or obstacles that developers must face. Uncertainty in global economic conditions is one of the factors that contributes to obstacles in the housing industry.

Queen Cempaka Hill Housing is one of the housing complexes in Jember Regency, more precisely in the Gebang area. Product quality, price and promotion are very important in carrying out marketing strategies to increase customer satisfaction at Queen Cempaka Hill Housing. Customer satisfaction is the basic level of consumer feelings from a service or product quality that has been obtained by comparing what is received and the desired expectations in accordance with consumer needs. Product quality, price and promotions have an influence on customer satisfaction with a product to be purchased. The company uses product quality as the main focus in running its business. A company will be able to survive in the midst of business competition if the company is able to provide quality products and continues to

make improvements to this quality continuously. This will make customers buy the product, and will even make repeat purchases if the customer is satisfied with the quality of the product. Customer satisfaction is one measure of a company's success which will have an impact on sales levels. When customers feel satisfied, the customer will buy the product offered and will even buy the product again, thereby creating customer loyalty.

Price is the amount of money exchanged for a product and service that consumers need (Kotler & Armstrong, 2016). Price is something that plays an important role in facing competition, where in its application you do not only look at competitors' products but also have to adjust the price that will be set to the quality of a product. Promotion is communication that provides explanations and convinces potential consumers about a product with the aim of getting attention and convincing potential customers (Buchari, 2007).

Many previous studies discussing product quality and customer satisfaction have been carried out. Research conducted by (Pusparani & Rastini, 2014) with the title "The Influence of Product Quality and Brand Image on Consumer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty of Canon Digital Single Lens Reflex (DSLR) Cameras in Denpasar City" and the results were that product quality and brand image had an indirect effect directly on customer loyalty through consumer satisfaction, and consumer satisfaction has a positive and

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significant effect on customer loyalty. Research conducted by (Chaerudin & Syafarudin, 2021; Mahsyar & Surapati, 2020; Naini et al., 2022; Putro et al., 2014), (Hakim, 2021; Lenzun et al., 2014; Wantara & Tambrin, 2019) , (Izzuddin & Muhsin, 2020), (Setiawan et al., 2016), (Munisih & Soliha, 2015), also show that product quality has an impact on customer satisfaction.

There has also been a lot of research on the relationship between price and customer satisfaction. Research (Ariska et al., 2020) with the title "The Impact Of Service Quality, Price, Products, And Trust On "Kober Mie Satan" Consumer Satisfaction" and the results showed the positive influence of the service quality, price, products and the customer beliefs by simultaneous and partial customer satisfaction on Kober Mie Satan Jember East Java Indonesia. Research conducted by (Bilgies, 2017; Novrianda, 2016; Oktarini, 2020; Sholikhah & Hadita, 2023; Wariki et al., 2015), (Setyawati et al., 2018), (Budiyono et al., 2022), (Qomariah et al., 2020), (Surjaatmadja et al., 2019), (Anggriana et al., 2017), (Juanamasta et al., 2019), (Rosalina et al., 2019), (Yanuar et al., 2017), (Maimunah, 2020), (Yulisetiari & Prahasta, 2019), (Mahendra et al., 2019), (Fahrurrozi et al., 2020), (Iriyanti et al., 2016), (Nikmah et al., 2022), (Qomariah et al., 2024), also discusses the issue of the impact of price on customer satisfaction.

There has also been a lot of research on the relationship between promotion and customer satisfaction. Research conducted by (Setyaningsih & Murwatiningsih, 2017) with the title "The Influence of Motivation, Promotion and Destination Image on Visitor Satisfaction Through

Visitor Decisions" and the results are that the higher the level of motivation, promotion and destination image, the more it can influence the decision to visit. impact on visitor satisfaction. Research conducted by (Susilo et al., 2018) with the title "Analysis of the Effect of Price, Service Quality, Promotion, and Trust on Consumer Satisfaction with the Decision to Visit as an Intervening Variable at the Amanda Hills Hotel Bandungan", and the results are partially price, quality service, promotion, and trust influence visiting decisions and consumer satisfaction. Research by (Mardiyani & Murwatiningsih, 2015) with the title "The Influence of Facilities and Promotions on Visitor Satisfaction Through Visiting Decisions as Intervening Variables at Semarang City Tourist Attractions", and the results are that facilities and promotions have a direct effect on visitor satisfaction at Semarang City tourist attractions, decisions visiting has a direct influence on satisfaction, facilities and promotions have an influence on satisfaction through the decision to visit as an intervening variable. Other research that also discusses promotion issues with customer satisfaction was carried out by: (Lenzun et al., 2014), (Juniantara & Sukawati, 2018), (Sanosra et al., 2022), (Wibowo et al., 2021), (Qomariah et al., 2021).

This research was conducted to find the impact of product quality, price and promotion on customer satisfaction at Queen Cempaka Hills Housing in Jember Regency. Thus, the aim of this research is to determine and analyze the variables of product quality, price and promotion on customer satisfaction.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPED

H1: Product quality has a positive impact on customer satisfaction.

H2: The price of goods has a positive impact on customer satisfaction.

H3: Promotions carried out have a positive impact on customer satisfaction.

METHODS

The method used in this research is to use qualitative methods and literature studies, namely by reviewing literature books and previous research that are in accordance with the theory discussed, especially in the scope of marketing management. In qualitative research, literature reviews are used consistently with methodological assumptions. This means that it must be used inductively so that it does not direct the questions asked by the researcher. One of the main reasons for conducting qualitative research is that the research is exploratory in nature. This research attempts to develop a hypothesis related to the themes of product quality, price and promotion which are related to customer satisfaction at Queen Cempaka Hills Jember Housing. Data was obtained based on secondary data originating from previous research.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Influence of Product Quality on Customer Satisfaction

Product quality can be interpreted as the ability of the product to carry out its function which includes durability, reliability or progress, strength, ease of packaging and product repair and other characteristics (Kotler & Armstrong, 2019). Queen Cempaka Hills Housing is one of the many housing complexes in Jember Regency. Product quality has a big influence on the housing industry, and Queen Cempaka Hills Housing offers good quality housing products so that it can compete with other housing developments. Product quality is not only in finished house products, but product quality also starts from the initial stages of housing construction, namely from the planning stage, design stage, construction stage, occupancy stage, operation and maintenance stage. Research that discusses the relationship between product quality and job satisfaction, among others, was conducted by (Pusparani & Rastini, 2014) stating that product quality and brand image have an indirect effect on customer loyalty through consumer satisfaction, and consumer satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on customer loyalty. Research (Putro et al., 2014) with the title "The Influence of Service Quality and Product Quality on Customer Satisfaction and Consumer Loyalty of the Happy Garden Surabaya Restaurant" and the results are an assessment of product quality with the lowest assessment being that the restaurant offers larger portions than other restaurants. Research conducted by (Sujadi & Wahyono, 2015) with the title "The Influence of Innovation and Product Quality on Consumer Loyalty of Teh Botol Sosro With Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable", and the results are that there is a direct or indirect influence of product innovation and product quality variables on loyalty Teh Botol Sosro consumers through satisfaction as an intervening variable. Research conducted by (Hakim, 2021) with the title "Effect of Product Quality and Service Quality on Customer Loyalty with Customer Satisfaction as an Intervening

Variables (Case Study on the Tirta Jasa Lampung Selatan Regional Company (PDAM))" and the result is product quality has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction and also on customer loyalty. Research that also discusses the problem of the relationship between product quality and customer satisfaction was conducted by (Bailia et al., 2014), (Izzuddin & Muhsin, 2020).

The Influence of Product Prices on Customer Satisfaction

Product price is one of the important variables in marketing strategy which has a significant effect on customer satisfaction (Qomariah, 2016). The price offered must reflect the value received by customers and must be commensurate with the quality of the products and services provided. In the context of Queen Cempaka Hills Housing, housing product prices that are competitive and in line with consumer expectations will contribute greatly to customer satisfaction. Price is the amount of money that consumers must pay to obtain a product or service. Determining the right price influences consumer perceptions of product value and, ultimately, influences the level of customer satisfaction. According to (Kotler & Keller, 2016), price is one of the factors that can influence consumer purchasing decisions. Prices that are too high can make consumers switch to competing products, while prices that are too low can create a negative impression of product quality. Research by (Qomariah et al., 2024), shows that prices that match product quality can increase customer satisfaction. This research is relevant to the situation at Queen Cempaka Hills Housing, where the prices set must reflect the quality of the building and facilities offered to ensure customers feel they are getting value for the money they spend. Research conducted by (Susilo et al., 2018) with the title "Analysis of the Effect of Price, Service Quality, Promotion, and Trust on Consumer Satisfaction with the Decision to Visit as an Intervening Variable at the Amanda Hills Hotel Bandung", and the results are that price, service quality, promotions, and trust influence visiting decisions and consumer satisfaction. Research conducted by (Wantara & Tambrin, 2019) with the title "The Effect of Price and Product Quality Towards Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty on Madura Batik", and the results are that the price is a significant and positive impact on customer satisfaction, the product quality is significant and positive impact on customer satisfaction, that the price is significant and positive impact on customer loyalty, that the customer satisfaction is significant and positive impact on customer loyalty, but the product quality is not significant and positive impact on loyalty. Research conducted by with the title "The Effect Of Product Quality, Service Quality, Price On Product Purchasing Decisions On Consumer Satisfaction", and the results of this research is the price proved to have a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction of medical devices products health. Research conducted by (Lenzun et al., 2014) with the title

"The Influence of Product Quality, Price and Promotion on Telkomsel Prepaid Card Customer Satisfaction", and the results are that simultaneously product quality, price and promotion have a significant effect on customer satisfaction.

The Effect of Promotions on Customer Satisfaction

Promotion is a strategy carried out by a business entity or organization to inform and remind the market about certain products. Promotions are carried out to increase sales, establish product identity, increase consumer loyalty, and tighten competition with competitors. Meanwhile (Kotler & Armstrong, 2016), states that promotion is a series of techniques used to achieve sales or marketing targets using effective costs by providing added value to products or services, either to intermediaries or users. A series of promotional activities are carried out to influence consumer attitudes and behavior. Without promotion, information about the product will not reach consumers. The relationship with promotions can influence consumer satisfaction, based on previous research conducted by (Wariki et al., 2015), which states that promotions have a positive effect on the variables of consumer satisfaction and consumer loyalty. Another research conducted by . Meanwhile, the results of other research which expressed a different opinion were carried out by Nathaza Gayatry Woen et al (2021) at Burger King Yogyakarta which stated that the promotion variable had no influence on consumer satisfaction, this was because Burger King promotions were only felt by some consumers. Queen Cempaka Hill Housing is housing that was built specifically for subsidized housing, the marketing segmentation aimed at the millennial generation which can be seen from the number of products sold, of the 300 units available, 85 units have been sold, spread across ages 20 to 20. 30 years (67 units) and ages 31 s.d. 44 years (18 units). Buyers from the millennial generation are usually looking for the first residence they own so that the prices and products delivered adjust to the needs of potential buyers. The promotion carried out is by creating advertisements on social media, this is in accordance with the marketing target of Queen Cempaka Hill housing for the millennial generation. This housing company carries out promotions on social media by emphasizing the motto "Everyone Can Have a Home" so as to give consumers the confidence to own their first home easily. In terms of price, the company provides competitive prices with competitors and provides discounts at certain moments such as religious holidays and independence day. The promotions that have been carried out can attract buying interest from the millennial generation which can be seen from all the units sold being buyers from the millennial generation. In this case, millennials tend to be active on social media so that the promotions carried out are right on target so they can attract consumer buying interest. In this way, promotions can have a positive effect on consumer satisfaction which can be seen from the number of units sold and the distribution of buyers

from the millennial generation.

CONCLUSION

1. Queen Cempaka Hills Housing offers quality housing products that pay attention to measurable indicators so that they have a very positive influence on customer satisfaction.
2. Determining the price for Queen Cempaka Hills Housing is based on several factors including construction costs, operational costs and the market price of the property similar so that this can indicate competitive prices and balance with the quality of home products which can increase customer satisfaction.
3. Queen Cempaka Hills Housing carries out promotions on social media by emphasizing the motto "Everyone Can Have a Home" so as to give consumers confidence in owning housing. Promotions carried out by the housing marketing team have a positive effect on customer satisfaction as evidenced by the product or house selling as many as 170 units out of 300 units.
4. It is hoped that product quality, price and promotion can increase customer satisfaction.

SUGGESTION

1. Determining product quality indicators, product prices and promotions must be considered properly so that they have a positive effect on customer satisfaction.

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